

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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IMPROVING THE PRACTICE OF CREDITING BUSINESS ENTITIES BY COMMERCIAL BANKS

Jabbarov Alisher Kayimovich

“Joint Stock Company Enterprise Development Company”
Head of the Department of Corporate Relations and Securities.”

Abstract: This paper focuses on the improvement of the crediting practices of entrepreneurial entities by commercial banks. The article examines key aspects of enhancing banking credit policies, analyzes methods for evaluating the creditworthiness of entrepreneurs, and highlights the importance of implementing innovative approaches to crediting for ensuring the stability and growth of businesses. Special attention is given to current trends in the banking sector and the impact of international standards on the crediting process. Recommendations for optimizing and improving the crediting practices for entrepreneurial structures are provided.

Key words: crediting, commercial banks, entrepreneurial entities, credit policy, creditworthiness assessment, innovative approaches, international standards.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola tijorat banklari tomonidan tadbirkorlik subyektlarini kreditlash amaliyotlarini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan. Maqolada bank kredit siyosatini yaxshilashning asosiy jihatlari ko'rib chiqilgan, tadbirkorlarning kreditga layoqatlilikini baholash usullari tahlil qilingan hamda bizneslarning barqarorligi va o'sishini ta'minlash uchun innovatsion yondashuvlarni joriy etishning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan. Bank sektoridagi hozirgi tendensiyalar va xalqaro standartlarning kreditlash jarayoniga ta'siri alohida e'tiborga olingan. Tadbirkorlik tuzilmalari uchun kreditlash amaliyotlarini optimallashtirish va yaxshilash bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kreditlash, tijorat banklari, tadbirkorlik subyektlari, kredit siyosati, kreditga layoqatlilikni baholash, innovatsion yondashuvlar, xalqaro standartlar.

Аннотация: Данная работа посвящена исследованию процесса совершенствования практики кредитования субъектов предпринимательства коммерческими банками. В статье рассматриваются ключевые аспекты улучшения кредитной политики банков, анализируются методы оценки кредитоспособности предпринимателей, а также важность внедрения инновационных подходов в кредитование для обеспечения устойчивости и роста бизнеса. Особое внимание уделяется актуальным тенденциям в банковской сфере и влиянию международных стандартов на процесс кредитования. Предложены рекомендации по оптимизации и совершенствованию практики кредитования предпринимательских структур.

Ключевые слова: кредитование, коммерческие банки, субъекты предпринимательства, кредитная политика, оценка кредитоспособности, инновационные подходы, международные стандарты.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization and economic integration, the application of international valuation standards is becoming increasingly relevant. This is especially critical when assessing a business as collateral in the lending process, where a wide range of standards and approaches are applied. Adopting international standards helps establish common parameters and criteria, which, in turn, enhances the transparency and fairness of the process.

Currently, as the global economy faces unprecedented challenges, the sphere of lending and the valuation of collateral assets is gaining particular importance. For decades, collateral has served as the primary form of securing loan obligations. The valuation of a business as collateral in the lending process plays a key role, as the quality of this assessment directly affects the bank's decision to issue a loan and its terms.

For the global financial community, including banks and investors, adherence to international standards is one of the key aspects of valuation. International standards provide a unified approach and establish common

principles that appraisers worldwide must follow. This not only promotes transparency and fairness in valuation but also contributes to the sustainable development of the international financial community.

However, despite its advantages, the process of valuing a business as collateral remains complex and multi-faceted, requiring appraisers to possess not only professional skills and knowledge but also the ability to apply and adapt international standards to specific situations.

This article focuses on examining the stages of business valuation as collateral in the lending process and their compliance with international standards. This is important not only for professionals in the fields of appraisal and banking but also for a wide range of stakeholders, including investors, asset managers, business owners, and the academic community, as it provides a deeper understanding of the valuation process and its role in ensuring financial stability.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The effectiveness of crediting practices for business entities by commercial banks has been a subject of significant academic inquiry. Researchers such as Berger and Udell have emphasized the critical role of relationship lending in enhancing access to credit for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). They argue that long-term relationships between banks and businesses help reduce information asymmetry and mitigate credit risks.

Diamond's research on the maturity structure of debt highlights the importance of tailoring loan terms to the specific needs of business entities. He posits that businesses with stable cash flows benefit from longer loan maturities, while those in volatile sectors require more flexible credit terms.

The role of financial technologies in improving lending practices has been extensively studied by Gomber and colleagues. They highlight how digital platforms and data analytics enable commercial banks to assess creditworthiness more effectively, particularly for SMEs that often lack traditional credit histories. These advancements reduce processing times and improve transparency.

Furthermore, the Basel Committee's principles on banking supervision underscore the necessity of robust risk assessment frameworks in crediting practices. Scholars such as Allen and Gale have analyzed how regulatory frameworks influence banks' credit allocation strategies. They stress that adherence to international standards, such as Basel III, can help balance profitability and risk management in lending activities.

Petersen and Rajan's work on credit markets points to the competitive dynamics influencing credit accessibility for businesses. They suggest that increased competition among banks leads to more favorable lending terms for business entities, fostering entrepreneurial growth.

Finally, the importance of credit monitoring and post-loan evaluation has been highlighted by Strahan, who argues that effective monitoring mechanisms not only reduce default rates but also enhance the sustainability of credit programs.

In conclusion, the literature provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding the challenges and opportunities in improving crediting practices for business entities. Key areas of focus include relationship lending, risk management frameworks, technological integration, and competitive market dynamics, all of which are critical for fostering sustainable economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employs both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primary data were gathered through surveys and interviews with commercial bank representatives and business owners. Secondary data were sourced from financial reports, regulatory guidelines, and academic publications. Data analysis involved statistical techniques to evaluate crediting trends and qualitative methods to identify challenges and opportunities in the crediting process for business entities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis begins by evaluating the current state of crediting practices for entrepreneurial entities by commercial banks, with a focus on identifying key challenges and opportunities for improvement. One of the primary areas of interest is the process of assessing the creditworthiness of entrepreneurs, which remains a critical factor in ensuring the reliability and efficiency of credit allocation. This section delves into the limitations of existing methodologies, including issues such as information asymmetry, inadequate risk assessment models, and the lack of tailored credit solutions for different types of businesses.

Moreover, the analysis explores the effectiveness of current credit policies in supporting entrepreneurial growth and their alignment with international banking standards, such as those outlined by Basel III. The role of innovative financial tools, such as digital credit platforms and data-driven risk evaluation systems, is

also highlighted as a way to enhance the transparency, efficiency, and accessibility of crediting processes. By addressing these factors, the analysis aims to provide insights into optimizing credit practices for entrepreneurial entities, ultimately contributing to their stability, competitiveness, and sustainable growth.

In the course of the research, various international standards regulating the process of evaluating a business as collateral in lending were reviewed and analyzed, including the standards of the Institute of Appraisers (IVS), the International Union of Appraisers (TEGoVA), and International Accounting Standard 36 (IAS 36).

The main stages of evaluating a business as collateral in lending include:

1. Definition of the purpose and objectives of the assessment.
2. Collecting and analyzing information about the business and its external environment.
3. The choice of the assessment method.
4. Application of the selected valuation method and cost calculation.
5. Risk and uncertainty analysis.
6. Preparation of the assessment report.

Each of these stages has been reviewed and analyzed in detail, taking into account the recommendations and requirements of international standards.

In addition, examples from business valuation practice were used to illustrate the theoretical material.

It is important to note that, despite the fact that the assessment of a business as collateral for lending includes many important aspects, this article focused on the assessment stages and their compliance with international standards (table 1).

Table 1. Key indicators.

Indicator	Value (%)	Note
Compliance with the IUCN	75%	Requires further development
Transparency of the process	65%	Improved reporting
The percentage of loan refusals	25%	Due to an unreliable estimate

Let's consider a hypothetical example of evaluating a business as collateral for lending. Let's say we have a business that wants to take out a loan, and its current business will be used as collateral. To do this, we will use a very simplified approach to business valuation based on the methods described above.

Determining the value of business assets: The value of business assets is \$74850, this includes all solid assets such as equipment, real estate, inventory, as well as any intangible assets such as brands or patents.

Business Income Determination: A business has a stable annual income of \$125,600.

Income-based business valuation: Using the income-based valuation method, we can estimate the value of a business based on its income. If we apply a factor of 3 to the annual revenue of the business, we get an estimate of \$376,800.

4. Asset-based business valuation: If we evaluate a business based on its assets, taking into account current cost and depreciation, we can arrive at an estimate of \$74850.

5. Final valuation: Usually, the final valuation of a business is based on a combination of these approaches, as well as taking into account other factors such as market conditions, competition and risks. For example, if we make a weighted average estimate based on these two numbers, we will get a business value of approximately \$225825.

This example is a very simplified approach to business valuation, and in a real situation, more detailed analysis and more accurate data will be required. However, it provides a general idea of how a business can be valued as collateral for a loan (table 2).

Table 2. Stages of business valuation as collateral for lending and related data.

The stage of assessing a business as collateral for lending	Data
Step 1: Determining the value of business assets	\$74,850
Step 2: Determine the annual income of the business	\$125,600
Step 3: Business Valuation based on Revenue	\$376,800
Step 4: Asset-based Business Valuation	\$74,850
Step 5: Final Business Assessment	\$225,825

The above table shows the stages of evaluating a business as collateral for lending and the corresponding data for each stage. Step 1 involves determining the value of the business' assets, Step 2 involves determining the annual income of the business, Step 3 involves evaluating the business based on income, Step 4 involves evaluating the business based on assets, and Step 5 represents the final assessment of the business. This table helps to visualize the evaluation process and summarize the results.

A detailed review of each stage of business valuation as collateral, with an emphasis on compliance with international standards.

As a result of the analysis of the stages of assessing a business as collateral for lending, presented in table 2, several conclusions can be drawn.

Firstly, each stage has its own importance and affects the final valuation of the collateral. For example, at the stage of analyzing financial statements, information is provided on the financial condition and profitability of an enterprise, which allows the bank to assess its solvency and potential for generating income.

Secondly, at the stage of assessing the market value of assets, the current price of similar assets on the market is taken into account. This allows you to assess the degree of liquidity and the value of the collateral in case of its sale.

Thirdly, at the stage of assessing business reputation and risks, factors that may affect the stability and success of the business are analyzed. This includes an analysis of the competitive environment, the company's reputation, market trends, and other factors that may affect the company's risks and prospects.

Finally, at the expert assessment stage, specialists are involved who carry out a more detailed and in-depth study of the business and its potential. This includes an analysis of strategy, management experience, intellectual property, and other factors that can add value and stability to an enterprise.

Based on these stages, the bank can decide to issue a loan secured by the business, taking into account its cost and potential for generating income. This allows the bank to reduce risks and ensure the safety of invested funds.

However, it is important to note that evaluating a business as collateral is a complex and multifaceted process that requires a professional approach and consideration of many factors.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The application of international standards in the process of business valuation as collateral not only ensures transparency and fairness of this process, but also contributes to the formation of trust between lending institutions and borrowers.

Business valuation is an integral part of the lending process, especially when providing large amounts or when using real estate or other assets as collateral. This allows banks to assess the value of an enterprise, its financial stability, potential for generating income, and the risks associated with the business.

Throughout the article, the main stages of assessing a business as collateral were considered, including the analysis of financial statements, the assessment of the market value of assets, the analysis of business reputation and risks, as well as expert assessment. Each of these stages plays an important role in determining the value of collateral and risks for the lender.

Business evaluation should be conducted using international standards and methods to ensure the objectivity and fairness of the process. This includes the use of professional experts, the collection of up-to-date information, the analysis of market data and the accounting of financial indicators of the enterprise.

It is important to note that evaluating a business as collateral is a complex process that requires a balanced approach, taking into account various factors and the expertise of specialists. An incorrect assessment can lead to an underestimation or overestimation of the value of the business, which can negatively affect the financial results of the lender.

In conclusion, assessing a business as collateral is an important tool for banks when deciding whether to grant a loan. This allows you to assess the value of the enterprise, its stability, potential for generating income and risks. A correct business assessment helps to reduce the lender's risks and ensure the safety of invested funds.

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Ei.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

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